

Vanadium. Part XIV. Ligational Effects in Oxo-Vanadium (IV) Complexes

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Ligational effects in oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes has been studied by the infrared technique, when a five coordinated complex moves on to a six coordinated one or when variation is made in the groups of an already six coordinated complex. The base ligands are pyridine—and quinoline carboxylic acids. In most cases the vanadyl stretching frequency is lowered though the carboxyl bands remain almost unperturbed.

The vanadium oxygen multiple bond is associated with an energetic metal-oxygen stretching vibration and has attracted the attention of coordination chemists for some time¹. This vanadium-oxygen bond persists with some variation in the stretching frequency in all oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes and has served as a diagnostic tool for identification of a vanadium—oxygen bond. This multiple bond has been found to be affected sometimes to a very appreciable extent by the surroundings that the different ligands offer around vanadium. In general, the V=O stretching frequency is lowered on coordination due certainly to receiving electron charge cloud by the metal from the ligands. This apparently lengthens the V=O multiple bond. Some rough correlations between decreasing vanadyl stretching frequency and increasing V—O bond length has been observed².

Based on the extent of lowering of the stretching frequency attempts to develop some qualitative ligand series have been made. However, these ligand series do not exactly parallel the spectrochemical series, mainly because the first effect arises out of vibration whereas in the spectrochemical series octahedral ligand field splitting of the metal d—orbitals by the ligands is the effective cause. Coming to this lowering, mention has to be made of a few significant studies that have been made recently. The five coordinated monomer complex, bis acetylacetonate oxo-vanadium (IV) was treated in CHCl_3 by very large excess of ligands which could serve as donors in the sixth positions³. Those producing shifts of 48 cm^{-1} included pyridine, ammonia, ethylamine, ethylene diamine etc., whereas ligands such as thiourea, triphenyl phosphine, triphenylarsine failed to produce any shift at all. Some other ligands like aniline, tetrahydrofuran, dioxan produced shifts of about 23 cm^{-1} . However in the cases of $[\text{VO}(\text{Oxin})_2]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{an-bis-sal})_2]$ no shifts were observed. The authors have preferred for an explanation of this failure to assume a trigonal bi-pyramid structure for these two complexes for which they have claimed some dipole-moment support³. We are of the opinion that investigating the vanadyl stretching frequency by way of adding excess of ligand to act at the sixth coordination position is not entirely beyond criticism. The failures in these two cases might as well be attributed to a very

1. Barraclough *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.

2. (a) McGlynn *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.* 1961, 35, 105.

(b) Selbin, *Chem. Revs.*, 1965, 65, 153.

3. Selbin, Manning and Cessac. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 1259.

slow rate of reaction of the five coordinated species compared to fast reaction with the bis-acetylacetonate complex. Besides many such oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes are extremely susceptible to oxidation in presence of donor solvents. In case such oxidation occurs leading to an oxo-hydroxo vanadium (V) complex, there will be a very great lowering of the stretching frequency. Both such effects have been observed in our laboratory⁴.

We have, therefore, a feeling that comparison of lowering of the V-O stretching frequency should better be made with comparable complexes in solid crystalline form as nujol mull or by KBr disc techniques. An extensive study of fifty such oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes has been reported⁵ though there were only one or two examples where one could draw a comparison between a five coordinated species and a six coordinated one. However, in these cases there has been observed a shift ranging from 7- 32 cm^{-1} (Table I). Besides these above works another simultaneous study was published from our Laboratory reporting only one such example of pyridine coordination wherein an average shift of about 10 cm^{-1} was observed⁶. Mention may also be made of the shifting of the stretching frequency of bisbiguanide oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes. Although the complexes were not such as to offer a rightful comparison in the above lines, considerable lowering (about 65 cm^{-1}) was observed compared to $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{2+}$ and a correlation between the extent of lowering and the base strength of the ligands has been made⁶.

In the light of the above existing situation we consider that we have now at our disposal a large number of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes where a correlation might be sought between the lowering of the vanadyl stretching frequency (while taking the complex from a five coordinated one to a six coordinated species or changing some ligand environments in an already six coordinated species) and the nature of the donor ligands.

Besides, the various ligands that are being studied in our Laboratory, having the same functional groups namely a heterocyclic nitrogen and one or more COOH groups, favourably disposed so as to form a five or six membered ring around the metal, offered a new scope to see whether or not the effect of these changes in the ligational environments also influenced the vanadium carboxyl attachment. On the assumption that the five coordinated species is a square pyramid (for which there are some evidences in the literature)⁷ it is expected that the sixth ligand would exert some trans influence on the vanadyl oxygen resulting in some lengthening of the V-O bond. While doing so, it is not entirely unlikely that the electron density in the vanadium d-orbitals will be changed to some extent which may result in the metal carboxylate binding strength being modified. This last effect, if any, will be reflected in the carboxylate stretching frequency.

We present the results of the lowering of the V-O stretching frequency of our complexes along with a few comparable cases taken from recent literature data in Table I.

In the cases of pyridine and quinoline carboxylic acids we now have enough data to conclude that introduction of a donor ligand such as pyridine, α -picoline and dimethyl formamide certainly brings down further the V-O stretching frequency though not as

4. (a) Dutta and Lahiry, *This Journal*, 1964, 41, 546.

(b) Dutta and Lahiry, *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 67, 837.

5. Selbin, Holmes and McGlynn., *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 1359.

6. Ray, De and Poddar, *Ind. Jour. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 228.

7. Dodge, Templeton and Zalkin, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, 35, 55.

TABLE I

Vanadium oxygen stretching frequency in oxo-vanadium (IV) Complexes

Complex	V-O stretch cm ⁻¹	Complex	V-O stretch cm ⁻¹
1. [VO (acac) ₂]	996	13. [VO (8-Q) ₂ H ₂ O] H ₂ O	965
2. [VO (acac) ₂ Py]	964	14. [VO (8-Q) ₂ Anil]	965
3. [VO (dipy) ₂] (C ₁₀ H ₈) ₂	979,923	15. [VO (Pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	962
4. [VO (dipy) ₂ Cl] Cl	965,973 sh	16. [VO (Pic) ₂ (Py)]	958
5. [VO (dipy) ₂ Br] Br	958,972 sh	17. [VO (Lut) (H ₂ O) ₂] H ₂ O	980
6. [VO (O-phen) ₂] (C ₁₀ H ₈) ₂	987	18. [VO (H ₂ O) (Py) (Lut)]	915
7. [VO (O-phen) ₂ Cl] Cl	982,960 sh, 908	19. [VO (Py) (Lut)]	910
8. [VO (O-phen) ₂ Br] Br. H ₂ O	981,984 sh, 908	20. [VO (Anil) (Lut)]	970
9. [VO (2-Q) ₂ H ₂ O]	977	21. [VO (Lut) (O-phen)] H ₂ O	978
10. [VO (2-Q) ₂ Py]	970	22. [VO (Lut) (dipy)] H ₂ O	967
11. [VO (2-Q) ₂ (α-pic)]	960	23. [VO (Lut) (O-phen-diam)]	972
12. [VO (2-Q) ₂ (D.M.F.)]	960	24. [VO (Lut) (acacH)]	981

acacH=acetylacetonate; Py=Pyridine; dipy=α-α'-dipyridil; O-phen=orthophenanthroline; 2-QH=Quinoline 2-carboxylic acid; Pic=Picoline; DMF=Dimethyl formamide; Anil=Aniline; PicH=Picolinic acid; Lut H₂=Lutidinic Acid; 8-QH=Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid; O-phen-diam=Ortho-phenylene diamine.

much as observed in the case of vanadyl acetylacetonate. The pyridine and quinoline carboxylic acids being superior σ-donors will certainly have passed on more electron density to vanadium so that introduction of pyridine, picoline or dimethyl formamide cannot be expected to bring about as much lowering. Aniline in this respect appears to be offering very poor ligational effect.

We have also studied a very powerful tridentate ligand, namely, pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid. The aquo complex shows a vanadyl band at 980 cm⁻¹ but when one of the two coordinated aqua molecules is replaced by a stronger donor pyridine there is a tremendous lowering to 915 cm⁻¹. This means that coordinated pyridine relays considerable electron density to vanadium, which effect gets even strengthened when we take off the remaining aqua molecule from the coordination zone resulting in a profound colour change from green to intense navyblue⁸. The literature does not record any such extreme lowering of the vanadyl frequency, nor any discussion on tridentate functioning ligands. However aniline (found to offer poor ligational effect for the above bidentate ligands) stays almost as much ineffective in the case of lutidinic acid. With respect to the heterochelates we observe very little lowering giving us the impression that the bidentates create only as much ligational environment as produced by two *cis* aqua molecules. This is also in keeping with the lower base strengths of such ligands compared to pyridine⁹.

Table II records the carboxylate frequencies of the free ligands and the corresponding oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes.

8. Dutta and Ghosh, *This Journal*, 1967, **41**, 273.

9. Basolo and Pearson, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions". John Wiley, 1958, p. 120.

TABLE II

Compound	COO-stretching, cm^{-1}
1. Quinoline-2-carboxylic Acid	1700
2. $[\text{VO} (2\text{-Q})_2 (\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	1630
3. $[\text{VO} (2\text{-Q})_2 (\text{p-pic})]$	1630
4. $[\text{VO} (2\text{-Q})_2 (\text{DMF})]$	1625
5. Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid	1700
6. $[\text{VO} (8\text{-Q})_2 (\text{H}_2\text{O})] \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1625
7. $[\text{VO} (8\text{-Q})_2 (\text{Anil})]$	1625
8. Pyridine-2-Carboxylic Acid	1710
9. $[\text{VO} (\text{Pic})_2 (\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	1650
10. $[\text{VO} (\text{Pic})_2 (\text{Py})]$	1630
11. Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic Acid	1720
12. $[\text{VO} (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 (\text{Lut})] \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1625
13. $[\text{VO} (\text{H}_2\text{O}) (\text{Pv}) (\text{Lut})]$	1625
14. $[\text{VO} (\text{Anil}) (\text{Lut})]$	1625
15. $[\text{VO} (\text{Lut}) (\text{O-phen})] \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1630
16. $[\text{VO} (\text{Lut}) (\text{p-dipy})] \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1630
17. $[\text{VO} (\text{Lut}) (\text{O-phen-diam})]$	1625

Abbreviations as under Table I

A survey of the carboxyl stretching frequency indicates that introducing donor groups in the sixth coordination position leaves the attachment of a COO group to vanadium definitely unaffected. This leads us to conclude that based on a square pyramid structure for the five coordinated species, the ligand in the sixth position exerts merely a trans effect on the vanadyl oxygen and makes no impression on the planar ligands cis with respect to the incoming donor. Similar reasonings may also be offered for the heterochelates.

EXPERIMENTAL

The complexes were synthesized by the standard procedures developed in our Laboratory during the last several years^{8,10}. IR spectra were studied in all cases as nujol mull and a few checks were made as KBr disc. Comparison however, has been restricted to mull studies in nujol to draw parallelism from other works.

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